

REVIEW

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Land use land cover (LULC) analysis in Nigeria: a systematic review of data, methods, and platforms with future prospects

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Abstract

Understanding land use and land cover (LULC) classification is critical for addressing environmental and human needs, particularly in developing countries. Nigeria is a developing country experiencing rapid population growth and economic development leading to increased LULC changes. While many studies have been done on LULC changes, there is a need for a comprehensive review of existing knowledge and limitations of LULC analyses in Nigeria. Hence, using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses method, this review paper presents a systematic review of LULC analyses in Nigeria by examining the adopted remote sensing data, pre-classified global and regional LULC maps, and classification and validation methods. This paper draws attention to the significant growth in LULC studies and highlights a need for awareness and access to existing and readily available LULC data. This review provides a broad overview of LULC data, classification methods, focus, scale, and constraints associated with LULC analysis in Nigeria. Also, it provides probable solutions to the challenges and GEE-based LULC classification scripts. There is a need to create and prioritize a national LULC data repository to ensure sustainable land monitoring and management in Nigeria. This will facilitate the spatial and temporal assessment of LULC at different scales and regions. High-resolution imagery and advanced classification methods such as deep learning need to be adopted to ensure accurate land cover analysis at different scales. Also, increased awareness programs, collaboration, and capacity-building initiatives will be beneficial to addressing current and emerging challenges related to LULC studies in Nigeria.

Keywords Land use land cover, Remote sensing, Classification, Nigeria, GEE

Background

Land use and Land cover (LULC) represent distinct yet interrelated concepts, reflecting both human use and the physical characteristics of the land (Olorunfemi et al.

2020; Nedd et al. 2021; Afolabi et al. 2021; Akaolisa et al. 2023). Specifically, “land use” describes how people use land for different purposes including production, recreation, habitat preservation, and wildlife management (Innocent Abbas 2013; Rajendran et al. 2020; Marufuzzaman et al. 2021; Mephors et al. 2021), while “land cover” is the observable features of Earth’s top layer, including plants, water, bare soil, urban infrastructure, etc. (Koko et al. 2022). The detection of LULC changes is increasingly crucial due to its impact on human needs and the environment (Afolabi et al. 2021), and it is vital for both understanding landscape dynamics and achieving sustainable management practices (Akaolisa et al. 2023). In

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developing countries or regions, economic and industrial development can exacerbate LULC changes, thus, leading to climate change, erosion, landslides, deforestation, land degradation, and biodiversity loss (Hasan et al. 2020; Zhang and Li 2022). Understanding LULC changes in such regions is necessary for managing natural resources, assessing environmental conditions, and creating policies for climate change mitigation.

Nigeria is an example of a developing country in the western region of Africa experiencing rapid population growth and LULC changes. According to Adesola et al. (2024), Nigeria is the most populated country in Africa with a population of 218.5 million and a total area of 923,769 km². Over the years, due to the high birth rate, Nigeria has been undergoing a rapid increase in population growth and is currently the seventh most populated country in the world. It has been projected that by 2050, Nigeria's population will be the third largest in the world, surpassing the United States. In 2019, Nigeria's urban population increased to 51.2% from 29.7% in 1990 (Faisal Koko et al. 2021), implying a spatial increase of built-ups in urban areas. The rapid population growth puts pressure on the country's limited natural land cover such as forests, leading to land fragmentation, deforestation, and climate change. The pattern and extent of natural ecosystem loss have been linked to direct and indirect human activities such as agricultural expansion, urban sprawls, clearcutting, firewood collection, and road construction among others (Olajuyigbe 2018; Adeyemi et al. 2022; Fashae et al. 2022; Oyediji and Adenika 2022).

Over the years, there have been significant improvements in remote sensing data (coarse to fine-resolution imagery and temporal resolution), classification methods (traditional to deep-learning classifiers), and platforms (stand-alone software to cloud-computing platforms) used in LULC analysis. Also, assessing the accuracy of LULC classification has evolved with different evaluation metrics and methods. Numerous studies have investigated LULC dynamics as primary or secondary objectives in Nigeria, utilizing various remote sensing techniques, geographic information systems (GIS), and statistical modeling approaches. These studies have explored themes such as deforestation (Aliyu et al. 2020; Fitz et al. 2022; Fabolude et al. 2023), urban expansion (Adebayo et al. 2019; Samuel and Atobatele 2019), agricultural land use change (Duke et al. 2022; Abubakar et al. 2023), and ecosystem degradation. The growing importance of LULC information in addressing environmental challenges and its wide application in Nigeria necessitates a thorough synthesis of existing research. This review filled a critical knowledge gap by providing an overarching understanding of LULC analysis, identifying areas for future research, and exploring emerging trends. Notably,

a comprehensive review of this nature has not been previously undertaken. Therefore, we examined peer-reviewed articles published over 13 years and presented a broad overview of LULC data, analysis methods, focus, scale, and constraints associated with LULC analysis in Nigeria. Furthermore, it provides relevant future directions and GEE-based LULC classification scripts.

Main text

Methodology

We queried the Web of Science and Scopus databases for peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2010 and 2023 to assess Nigeria's land use land cover mapping trends and capacity. We adopted the new systematic review's Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA; Page et al. (2021)) concept. In the WoS database, a Boolean keyword search was carried out using “(land use OR land cover OR LULC OR landuse OR landcover OR change detection) AND (Nigeria)”, while in the Scopus database, the “(land-use OR land-cover OR lulc OR landuse OR landcover OR change-detection)” keyword was used with Nigeria specified as the geographic region.

The initial searches from both databases yielded 1509 records (WoS: 930 and Scopus: 579, accessed on 01/23/2024) which were merged, and the *Revtools* package (Westgate 2019) in R (R Core Team 2023) was used for duplicate removal and paper screening. Duplicates were removed manually through the R shiny interface created by the *screen_duplicates* function. This was followed by manually screening the Title and Abstracts through the R shiny interface created by the *screen_abstract* function. Two reviewers performed the screening while five reviewers did the data extraction independently. All articles that carried out LULC analysis using remote sensing data or that adopted pre-classified LULC data for a study within Nigeria were selected. Figure 1 shows the PRISMA diagram for the paper screening and selection. The analysis did not include studies that used vegetation indices as LULC proxies.

Results

The total number of relevant studies was 206, and the findings were reported under two categories. The first category covered (1) the trends in LULC publications over the years, (2) whether LULC data was developed (Created LULC Maps), or pre-classified data (Available LULC Maps) was used, and (3) the focus of the analysis. The second category focused on articles that classified LULC in their studies (192). Under this category, we analyzed and reported the (1) characteristics and sources of data used in LULC classification, (2) areas

Fig. 1 The PRISMA flow diagram of peer-reviewed article selection

of interest, (3) classification methods, (4) analysis platform (software used for analysis), (5) validation, and (6) accuracy.

First category

Publication trends

Figure 2 shows the trend in publications based on the source of LULC data from 2010 to 2023. The number of articles published on LULC analysis increased significantly over the years starting from 2019, with the highest number (38) published in 2022. Additionally, findings revealed that 14 studies used available LULC data while 192 developed their own LULC data. Figure 2 shows the trend in the use of publicly available LULC dataset which did not start until 2016 and peaked in 2022.

Pre-classified land use land cover datasets

As mentioned earlier, 14 (6.8%) articles used the publicly available LULC dataset. Table 1 shows the list of the different regional and global LULC data used by the authors. The LULC data ranged from a fine resolution of 10 m to a coarse resolution of 2 km. While two datasets are specifically made for the African continent (i.e., European Space Agency (ESA) Africa Land Cover and West Africa LULC), others are global LULC datasets. The West Africa and ESA global LULC datasets, with spatial resolutions of 2 km and 20 m, respectively, were the most widely used among all LULC datasets.

Fig. 2 Frequency of peer-reviewed articles on LULC and the source of LULC data based on database search from 2010 to 2023

Table 1 Publicly available LULC datasets used by authors from 2010 to 2023

Land Cover	Frequency	Extent	Resolution (m)
ESA Africa LC	2	Africa	20
Moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer (MODIS) Land cover dynamics	2	Global	500
Globeland30	2	Global	30
West Africa LULC	3	West Africa	2000
ESRI sentinel LULC	1	Global	10
Copernicus LULC	1	Global	100
ESA global LULC	3	Global	300

Land use land cover classification focus

The total articles were grouped into two to determine the focus of LULC analysis. The first group represents studies that primarily examined the LULC of a study area within a specific timeframe or over a certain period (hereafter, referred to as primary). Conversely, the other group represents studies that used LULC data as input to achieve other research objectives such as biodiversity assessments, hydrological studies, etc. (hereafter, referred to as secondary). Figure 3 shows that 26% (n=54) of the studies focused primarily on LULC analysis while 74% (n=152) used LULC data as an input to achieve their main objectives.

Fig. 3 The focus of the LULC analysis from all the peer-reviewed articles (n=206)

Second category

Under this category, 192 articles that developed LULC data were further analyzed for the characteristics of the remote sensing data used, methods of analysis, and accuracy.

Data characteristics

The different remote sensing data types used in LULC analysis in Nigeria are shown in Fig. 4. Among all the 192 articles, 173 used Landsat, 13 combined different data, 3 used Sentinel, while Geo-Eye1, MODIS, and drone images were used individually by one article. Based on temporal availability and public accessibility, Landsat

Fig. 4 Remote sensing data used for LULC analysis

Fig. 5 Sources of remote sensing data used in LULC analysis within Nigeria. The results are from 192 peer-reviewed articles where NR represents Not Reported; GEE: Google Earth Engine; GLCF: Global Land Cover Facility; AWS: Amazon Web Services

was the most (n=173) used satellite data in classifying LULC over the years in Nigeria, followed by Sentinel (n=3). The authors also combined different satellite data, especially Landsat and Sentinel in LULC analysis. With a frequency of one, high-resolution data from drone and commercial satellites have been used in LULC classification in Nigeria. From in-depth analysis, only 5 studies combined NigerSat (i.e., a Nigerian satellite) with other satellite data.

Figure 5 shows the different platforms from which Nigerian researchers assessed the satellite and aerial images used for LULC analysis. Landsat, the most used satellite data was majorly sourced (145 articles) from the Earth Explorer platform. A total of 24 studies did not report the data source used in LULC classification. Seven studies accessed data within the Google Earth Engine platform, six sourced data from combined sources, and four, used the former Global Land Cover Facility website before the platform was shut down. Two studies got their data from a Nigerian platform such as a university remote sensing department and government agencies. Also, one study used the Amazon Web Service platform to source remote sensing data, while another study used aerial images collected with their drone.

Methods

The different software used in classifying images for LULC analysis in Nigeria is shown in Fig. 6. Out of 192 articles, 70 papers used ArcMap/ArcGIS Pro in LULC

Fig. 6 Software used by authors for LULC classification. ENVI: Environment for Visualizing Images; ERDAS: Earth Resources Data Analysis System; GEE: Google Earth Engine; QGIS: Quantum GIS; ILWIS: Integrated Land and Water Information System; NR: Not Reported

classification. This was followed by Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI) and Earth Resources Data Analysis System (ERDAS Imagine) which were used in 30 and 29 studies respectively. TerrSet (formerly IDRISI), Google Earth Engine, Integrated Land and Water Information System (ILWIS), Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS), and Ecognition were used for classification in 20, six, four, three, and one studies respectively. A total of 29 studies did not report on the software used for classification.

Figure 7 shows the different methods used in LULC classification. The most used supervised and unsupervised methods were the Maximum Likelihood classifier with 60.4% (n=116) and Iso-Cluster with 4.7% (n=9), respectively. Machine learning methods such as Random Forest and Support Vector Machine (SVM) were only used in six and two articles respectively. Supervised, Unsupervised, Object-based, and Pixel-based categories in Fig. 7 show the number of papers that did not specify the classifier used but reported either of the broad classification categories.

The 192 peer-reviewed articles were analyzed to determine the location of the study area and categories. The former explains the region within Nigeria where the LULC analysis was carried out while the latter classified the study ecosystem as habitat or non-habitat. Habitat represents natural or semi-natural ecosystems such as forests, farmlands, mangroves, mining areas, and water bodies. In contrast, non-habitat represents LULC analysis carried out in a city, local government, state, or the entire country. In this review, the southern region comprises south-west, south-south, and south-east, and the northern region comprises Nigeria's north-central, north-west,

Fig. 7 LULC Classification Methods used in 192 peer-reviewed articles used in this study. RF: Random Forest; PBC: Pixel-based classification; OB: Object-based; MD: Minimum Distance; ML: Maximum Likelihood; SAM: PCM: Parallelepiped Classification Method; SAM: Spectral Angle Mapper; SVM: Support Vector Machine; DF: Developed Framework; KMC: K-Means Clustering; NR: Not Reported

and north-east geopolitical zones. The southern region had the highest (n=130) LULC study location while the northern region had the lowest (n=60). In both regions, LULC classification focused mainly on human settlements (42.7%) rather than natural/semi-natural (22.4%) habitats (Fig. 8).

Validation of classified maps is critical to ascertain the accuracy and reliability of such maps. Figure 9 shows the number of articles that validated their classified maps based on the focus of the LULC analysis. Out of the 192 studies, only 53.1% (n=102) validated their LULC maps. Based on the LULC analysis focus (primary or secondary), 138 studies used LULC as input data (secondary) and from this, only 62 studies validated their classification while 76 studies did not validate their classification. Out of 54 studies that focused primarily on LULC classification as their main objective, 40 studies validated

Fig. 8 Regions of LULC analysis within Nigeria with the study area category (Habitat and Non-Habitat). Habitat includes natural and semi-natural habitats like forests, farmlands, mangroves, mining areas, and water bodies, and non-habitats represent LULC carried out in a city, local government, state, or the entire country

Fig. 9 Validation of LULC maps based on primary and secondary objectives. Primary: The authors' main objective was LULC; Secondary: LULC data was used as input data to achieve their main objective

their LULC maps while 14 did not validate their classified maps.

As mentioned above, only 102 out of 192 studies validated their classified maps. The accuracy level achieved is shown in Fig. 10. Based on in-depth analysis, the major sampling methods used for validation include simple random and stratified random sampling. 87.3% (n=89) achieved an accuracy greater than 80% while 13 achieved between 61 and 80% accuracy.

Discussion

Trend and focus of LULC data

This paper presents a comprehensive review of LULC analysis within Nigeria. Our analyses, covering 13 years (2010–2023) revealed a significant growth in LULC publications in Nigeria, especially from 2019 onwards. This indicates a growing interest and emphasis on understanding LULC dynamics, especially with the sporadic increase in population and biodiversity loss. Furthermore, most studies (93.2%) developed their own LULC data through classification while only a few (6.8%) utilized publicly available LULC datasets. This indicates a potential lack of awareness and access to existing and readily available LULC data. This trend is illustrated in research conducted by (Olorunfemi et al. 2020; Akin-tunde-Alo and Komolafe 2022; Gilbert and Shi 2023), where authors generated their datasets tailored to specific regions within Nigeria. While locally-developed LULC classification tends to have high accuracy, global or regional LULC data can support large-scale analysis, can be used by researchers with limited resources, and mostly has a higher number of relevant land cover classes. Given the improvements in spatial, spectral, and temporal resolutions of remote sensing data, coupled with advanced classification techniques like deep learning, there are publicly available LULC datasets with higher spatial resolution and accuracy relevant at different scales (Zheng et al. 2021).

Fig. 10 Accuracy level from 102 studies that validated their classified maps

LULC products provide relevant information for environmental and social studies. Our findings showed how instrumental LULC analysis is in shaping environmental research in Nigeria. Interestingly, 74% of the reviewed publications utilized LULC data not merely for informational purposes or LULC map development, but as a foundational input to accomplish their primary research objectives. Some of the primary objectives include modeling (Etuk et al. 2023), environmental and social impact assessment (Daramola et al. 2018; Makinde and Agbor 2019; Okeke et al. 2022; Ibitoye et al. 2022), disaster and risk mapping (Oladotun 2021; Durowoju et al. 2022; Alimi et al. 2023), and other environmental modeling analyses (Ohiambe et al. 2019; Eludoyin and Adewole 2020; Obiahu and Elias 2020). This reflects stakeholders' diverse needs and interests across the natural resource and environmental management sectors. By incorporating LULC analysis as a basis of their work, researchers gain a deeper understanding of current environmental and social challenges such as land use changes, biodiversity loss, urban expansion, deforestation, and climate change. This knowledge supports informed decisions and promotes sustainable development in Nigeria.

LULC data and sources

This review showed a clear preference for satellite-based data, especially Landsat imagery for LULC analysis at different scales and ecosystems in Nigeria. Given its availability and long-time coverage of over 40 years, Landsat imagery is the most prevalent and used satellite imagery among researchers in Nigeria. Over the years and globally, Landsat satellites have been providing imagery with spectral resolutions covering the visible, infrared, and thermal regions of the electromagnetic spectrum and have been used alone or in combination with other data for a broad range of applications. Furthermore, Landsat data was accessed primarily on the USGS platform—EarthExplorer/Glovis which is largely attributed to the platform being the major archive of the data. Other relevant factors such as easy navigation, access to free and pre-processed data, search and text-based queries, and bulk downloads promote the useability of the platform. Also, the platform allows file upload, visualization of the datasets, and the associated metadata access. However, there are some gaps and potential limitations associated with relying on remote sensing data such as Landsat. For example, cloud cover and availability of images due to long revisiting time may affect Landsat use for LULC analysis, and the resolution may not be suitable for land cover analysis that requires detailed information.

Interestingly, we observed Nigeria's national satellite data, NigeriaSATS, have been underutilized for LULC analysis. This may stem from issues related to data

reliability and accuracy as highlighted by previous studies (Chima et al. 2017). Factors such as poor accessibility, lack of awareness, limited documentation, and inadequate metadata may have constrained the effective use of these datasets in LULC studies. Additionally, high-resolution satellite data like Sentinel and aerial images have not been well utilized. For Sentinel, this might be partly related to its low temporal coverage (Sentinel 2A and 2B were launched in 2015 and 2017 respectively) coupled with the lack of thermal images at a fine resolution. For aerial imageries, currently, there are no known national aerial data collection programs providing access to such datasets in Nigeria. Only one study in this review used unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) data and the study (Duke et al. 2022) was conducted by a non-profit and research-for-development organization.

LULC analysis

Software

As shown in Fig. 6, ArcMap/ArcGIS Pro, a proprietary GIS software, is the most used software for LULC classification. This could be associated with researchers' familiarity and comprehensive software functionalities in performing different LULC classification processes such as training data collection, change detection, and accuracy assessments. Also, the potential institutional licensing agreements make them readily available and facilitate their widespread usage. The two professional image processing software, ERDAS and ENVI are highly used for LULC analysis in Nigeria. ENVI and ERDAS are commercial software used for various geospatial analyses of lidar, multispectral, hyperspectral, and radar data. However, a study conducted by Di and Di (2011) compared both software and concluded that ENVI seems better in image classification while ERDAS excels in processing geometries.

In comparison to the preferred commercial software (ArcGIS Pro/ArcMap), very few studies used open-source software like QGIS (3 articles) for classification even though the software also aids in pre-processing satellite images, training deep learning models for image classification, and modeling land use change predictions (Ramadhan and Hidayati 2022). This indicates that researchers may be unfamiliar with QGIS or perceive that commercial software offers more advanced functionalities. Additionally, the availability of institutional licenses for commercial software could contribute to the lower usage of QGIS. Further research is needed to fully understand this trend and the potential barriers preventing the adoption of QGIS in Nigerian research environments.

Only six articles harnessed the cloud-computing platform, GEE, for LULC classification. With the growing need for geospatial applications and large-scale

monitoring, the GEE platform offers a free high-computing platform, numerous remote sensing and social-economic data, cloud-based storage, and sharing capabilities (Gorelick et al. 2017). However, this option has yet to be explored maximally by Nigerian researchers for LULC classification. This may be due to a lack of awareness and expertise in operating the platform or some GEE-based limitations. One of these limitations is the limited number of object-based image analysis and clustering algorithms available on the platform (Tamiminia et al. 2020). Nevertheless, GEE provides unique computational capabilities that support large-scale land monitoring.

LULC classifiers and accuracy assessment

The conventional maximum likelihood (ML) technique, a supervised classifier, is the most used classification method. This preference could be attributed to its computational efficiency and reliability, thus contributing to its popularity within the Nigerian research community. In addition, the classifier makes it easier to analyze a few land cover classes and efficiently distinguish between land covers. ML is a supervised classifier that computes the probability of a pixel belonging to a land cover type, and the pixel is assigned to the land cover type with the highest probability (Ayoade 2017). The ML classifier is widely available in many image-processing software (Lu and Weng 2007; Ahmad and Quegan 2012). Conversely, the adoption of deep learning models and supervised machine learning classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) is low with only a few studies employing these techniques (Ismail et al. 2023). In several land cover analyses, machine learning classifiers have demonstrated superior accuracy over conventional classifiers, and they are suitable for processing multidimensional data in less computational time (Thanh Noi and Kappas 2018; Theres and Selvakumar 2022). Furthermore, unlike conventional supervised algorithms, machine learning classifiers are unaffected by the statistical distribution of data. Despite these advantages, they are poorly adapted for LULC classification in Nigeria. The observed trend might be due to low expert knowledge, computational requirements, hyperparameter tuning, and a large amount of required training data.

Findings showed that a small percentage of the studies (1.56%) used more than one classifier for LULC classification. This is quite important as previous research has shown that comparing two or more classifiers provides better clarification on the appropriate classifier to adopt for a specific LULC analysis (Dabija et al. 2021). Also, there is a need for careful consideration of strengths and limitations when selecting an algorithm for LULC analysis, especially machine learning classifiers (Abubakar et al. 2023).

Accuracy assessment of LULC is essential to determine the reliability and suitability of the classification processes and the implications (margin of error) when used in decision-making. However, in this review, about 50% of the publications did not validate their classified maps, largely related to the secondary use of the LULC information in these studies. Given the dependency on LULC data, developing, or using publicly available LULC data requires accuracy assessment. For accuracy assessment, qualitative or quantitative methods can be used depending mostly on data availability and the end use of the LULC maps. The qualitative method involves visual comparison of ground features with the classified map, while the quantitative method uses reference datasets collected from the field or a high-resolution image to statistically evaluate the LULC accuracy. Generally, the confusion/error matrix is the widely used quantitative technique to determine the commission and omission errors and the overall accuracy (Stehman 1997).

LULC study area category

Across all the regions, most of the LULC studies focused more on classifying non-habitat compared to natural or semi-natural habitats. The classification of non-habitats such as settlements was targeted toward understanding urban growth and surface temperature (Ibrahim Mahmoud et al. 2016; Ogunjobi et al. 2018), urban heat island (Popoola et al. 2020), potential groundwater zones (Ajayi et al. 2022), landfill sites for waste management (Oyedele et al. 2022), mining impact (Afeni and Ibitolu 2018; Owolabi et al. 2021; Chukwuka et al. 2023), change detection, and LULC prediction (Adebayo et al. 2019; Idowu et al. 2020; Enoguanbhor et al. 2022). Some of these classification analyses (e.g., settlement expansion and urban growth) are essential precursors to understanding the impacts of anthropogenic activities on natural landscapes, while others (e.g., potential groundwater zones and landfill sites) provide information that improves social and environmental conditions. This shows the broad application of LULC information within Nigeria.

A few studies on the LULC classification of natural habitats focused on forests, wildlife corridors, and wetlands (Obiefuna et al. 2013; Suleiman et al. 2017; Odiji et al. 2022). Despite the relevance of non-habitat classification analysis, findings from this review suggest that more work needs to be done on classifying natural habitats. This is because natural habitats like forests and wetlands conserve biodiversity (Mengistu and Salami 2007), regulate microclimate, and contribute to socio-economic growth (Olajuyigbe 2018). However, in Nigeria, different forms of land degradation have contributed to the loss of forest cover (Khadijat et al. 2021; Adeyemi et al.

2022; Bukoye et al. 2023), making it an issue of concern (Junge et al. 2010). According to FAO (2020), less than 8% of Nigeria's total land area is currently forested, which consists of gazette reserves (1000), game reserves (32), national parks (7), and one strict nature reserve. Therefore, assessing the extent and changes of natural habitat coverage is critical for evaluating biodiversity conservation and ecosystem service.

The limitation of this review is the number of databases considered, and this is because some relevant publications in journals might not be indexed in the considered databases. Even though the objectives of this study were sufficiently answered and captured by the reviewed articles, the percentages or numbers might slightly change if other databases and platforms were considered. However, we believe the trends and patterns will still be the same.

Conclusions

Accurate LULC information is needed to ensure sustainable management of natural and man-made resources that are constantly subjected to climate change, degradation, and population pressure. The data, methods, and validation adopted in classifying land covers are essential for achieving high accuracy. In this section, we propose different data sources, advanced methods of classification, and solutions to some of the challenges in LULC mapping in Nigeria.

A national LULC data repository should be prioritized and created to ensure sustainable land monitoring and management in Nigeria. This will facilitate the spatial and temporal assessment of LULC at different scales and regions. Also, high-resolution imagery should be adopted in LULC classifications as it facilitates the clear distinction of land covers during supervised LULC training selection. Recently, the National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) in Nigeria has been providing high-resolution satellite images for free based on request. Based on certain guidelines, high-resolution panchromatic and multispectral images can be requested for non-commercial purposes (<https://central.nasrda.gov.ng/?p=2756>, Accessed on 25 May 2024). Sentinel-2, one of the European Space Agency satellites, provides high-resolution imagery with a temporal resolution of 2–5 days. The publicly available satellite data has 13 spectral bands (4 bands–10 m, 6 bands–20 m, and 3 bands–60 m) and can be harnessed for effective monitoring of land cover changes and trends in urban and rural environments. Also, new platforms like Nimbo Maps (<https://nimbo.earth/>, Accessed on 25 May 2024) provide monthly-based and global-scale access to preprocessed Sentinel imagery and a vegetation index (NDVI) by combining Sentinel-2 optical imagery with Sentinel-1 radar data. By using their available QGIS plugin (<https://>

plugins.qgis.org/plugins/assets/, Accessed on 25 May 2024), researchers can harness their monthly basemaps and earth online platforms for land cover monitoring and other remote sensing-based studies.

High-resolution satellite data from Planet Labs can be freely accessed through their Education and Research Program (<https://www.planet.com/markets/education-and-research/>, Accessed on 25 May 2024), especially by university researchers. The program enables non-commercial access to limited PlanetScope and RapidEye imagery (5000 km² per month). This will facilitate high-resolution LULC map production, fusion of Planet data with other satellite data, and land monitoring. Several studies have used satellite imagery accessed through Planet's educational program for different analyses (Miura et al. 2023; Veh et al. 2023; Ha et al. 2023). Access to high-resolution and analysis-ready data would facilitate effective monitoring of different natural and human-made landscapes at different scales.

To support environmental and large-scale monitoring, there are several publicly available global LULC maps with coarse–fine spatial resolutions. Some global LULC datasets were developed using machine and deep-learning techniques with relatively high accuracy. Regarding Nigeria, we curated a list of publicly available global and regional LULC datasets (moderate to fine resolution) (see Tables S1 and S2 in the supplementary section). With no current official national land cover dataset, global LULC data can be adapted to determine Nigeria's current land cover. However, before adopting global LULC information, factors like validation, temporal and spatial resolutions, bias, and suitability for the needed applications should be considered (Venter et al. 2022). High-resolution satellite, aerial imagery, or field data should be used to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the data. For validation data collection, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) Open Foris Collect Earth (<https://openforis.org/solutions/collect-earth/>, Accessed on 25 May 2024) and Collect Earth Online (<https://collect.earth/>, Accessed on 25 May 2024) are open-source desktop and web-based platforms that can be used. Also, depending on the scale of analysis, Nimbo Maps, GEE, Google Earth, and Sentinel data can be used.

LULC information is extracted from remote sensing images based on individual or a combination of spectral, textural, contextual, and geometric properties (Aryal et al. 2023). There are many LULC methods of classification with different performances. Cloud-based computing platforms like Google Earth Engine provide a unique advantage to researchers in terms of access to vast geospatial and socio-economic data, and a high-performance computing platform (Tamiminia et al. 2020). This platform supports geospatial analyses

like LULC classification and the availability of different machine learning classifiers on GEE. Researchers can access many datasets, analyze, and visualize LULC classifications, create Google Earth Engine Apps, and share their reusable codes with collaborators. Using public resources, we developed two free GEE reusable scripts for LULC classification based on a random forest classifier using Landsat and Sentinel data. The scripts, as templates, support satellite image selection, applying scaling factors, clipping to a region of interest, training and validating a random forest classifier, and accuracy assessment based on a confusion matrix. To demonstrate the workflow and facilitate the reusability of the scripts, we classified a study area (Omo Forest Reserve) using Landsat and Sentinel satellite data. The scripts are available on Github (https://github.com/Okikiola-Michael/random_forest_lulc) for people without a current GEE account and on GEE (https://code.earthengine.google.com/?accept_repo=users/alegbeleyeokiki/lulc) for users.

Conclusively, increased awareness programs, collaboration, and capacity-building initiatives will be beneficial to addressing current and emerging challenges related to LULC studies in Nigeria.

Abbreviations

ENVI	Environment for visualizing images
ERDAS	Earth resources data analysis system
ESA	European space agency
GEE	Google earth engine
LULC	Land use land cover
ML	Maximum likelihood
QGIS	Quantum GIS
RF	Random forest
SVM	Support vector machine

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42269-024-01286-z>.

Additional file1 (DOCX 586 KB)

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Author contributions

OMA searched and reviewed references, analyzed, and participated in writing the manuscript. YOR searched and reviewed references and participated in writing the manuscript. PS, AO, and OO reviewed references and contributed to manuscript writing. AAO reviewed and contributed to manuscript writing. All authors read and approve the final manuscript.

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Declarations

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